

Development of Institutional Climate Scale for Rating Teacher Education Institutions

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Abstract

This research paper deals with the development of a scale for assessing the institutional climate of teacher education institutions. The Likert's method of summative rating has been used to obtain a five point judgment on each item. Eleven dimensions of institutional climate have been identified after a critical appraisal of existing tools and related literature. The draft institutional climate scale consisted of 135 items. After the item analysis and tryout the final institutional climate scale took shape which has 64 items. The scale has content validity and reliability.

Introduction

In modern society most of the people spend their lives in an organisation of some kind and therefore they have first-hand experience of organisational life (Robertson & Cooper, 1983). Organisations are like complex open systems where surrounding affects the functioning of the organisation and organisation affects the surroundings. Pareek (2004) defined organisational climate as the perceived attributes of an organisation and its sub-systems as reflected in the way it deals with its members, associated groups and issues. Every organisation has some special attribute, it's some characteristics are unique and perhaps no two organisations or institutions can have exactly same set of organisational climate. In this research paper institutional climate stands for the organisational climate of the institutions which are engaged in academic work. Thus, institutional climate is the organisational climate of academic institutions.

The assessment of institutional climate is not an easy task, primarily because it can't be measured exactly as is the case with measurement of physical entities. Secondly, there is no near perfect tool or instrument available for its measurement. Thirdly, perception of institutional climate differs from individual to individual. Nevertheless, we may make an attempt to assessment the institutional climate by applying some suitable technique like rating scale, observation, interview etc. This research paper deals with the development of an institutional climate scale suitable for measurement of institutional climate of teacher education institutions in general and those engaged in preparing secondary and higher secondary teachers in particular.

Methodology

The present study deals with the development of a scale for assessment of institutional climate of teacher education institutions and establishing its reliability and validity.

(a) Identification of Dimensions and Framing of Statements

First of all, survey of the tools available for measuring institutional climate or organisational climate or school climate was made. Sharma (1982) identified eight dimensions of school climates: disengagement, alienation, esprit, psycho-physical hindrance, intimacy, control, production emphasis and humanised thrust. Sharma (1987) identified nine dimensions of organizational climate: scope for advancement, grievance handling, monetary benefits, participation in management, objectivity & rationality, recognition & appreciation, safety & security, training & education and welfare facilities. Anand (2004) developed school climate perception scale containing 48 items grouped into twelve domains. Miller (2008) identified ten dimensions of school climate: student-teacher relationships, security and maintenance, administration, students' academic orientation, student behavioural values, guidance, student peer relationships, parent and community-school relationships, instructional management and students activities. Tiller (2009) identified six dimensions of school climate: collaborative leadership, teacher collaboration, professional development, collegial support, unity of purpose and learning partnerships.

On the basis of these available tools eleven dimensions of institutional climate were identified. A brief description of these dimensions is as follows:

1. Resources-Physical and Human: It refers to the physical facilities in the institution, space in the institution and human resources needed to successfully accomplish the objectives of the institution.
2. Academic Activities: This refers to the availability of qualified teachers to teach all subjects/ papers, use of audio-visual aids and various aspects of teaching-learning process.
3. Co-curricular Activities: These are the activities undertaken by the institution to supplement curricular activities and help in the development of personality of students. This domain measures the participation of pupil-teachers in co-curricular activities, guidance by teacher-educators, celebration of national festivals etc.
4. Corporate Life: It refers to the life of pupil-teachers and teacher-educators as the members of the institution community, code of conduct, democratic functioning and development of community feeling etc.
5. Alienation from Institution: This domain of institutional climate scale explores teacher-educators' experience of institution as an unhappy place where they feel

inability to change the existing system, lack of participation in institutional decisions, feeling of boredom etc.

6. Satisfaction with Institution: This domain of the scale measures teacher-educators' appreciation of their institution and their contentment like feeling proud of being attached with the institution, liking for academic work and satisfaction in the teaching.

7. Interpersonal Relationships: It includes relationship between pupil-teachers and teacher-educators, teacher-educators readiness in solving problems of the pupil-teachers, impartiality in evaluation, encouraging pupil-teachers for achieving excellence.

8. Self-esteem and Sense of identity: Self-esteem refers to the feeling of self- worth and self-importance. It covers teacher-educators role in providing help to the community and pupil-teachers, due consideration to pupil-teachers' and teacher-educators' views and suggestions and looking with respect on them. Sense of identity refers to the identification of their self and relating the same to the others. It covers awareness of each other, mutual friendly relations, coordination etc.

9. Relevance of the Institution: This explores the consideration by teacher-educators regarding importance of the institution, importance of knowledge and skills imparted to pupil-teachers in their future life.

10. Sense of Achievement: This refers to the achievement of pupil-teachers in the examination and various activities.

11. Discipline: This domain of the scale refers to state of discipline in the institution and various measures taken by authorities to maintain discipline and encouragement for developing inner discipline in pupil-teachers etc.

Overall 135 items covering all eleven dimensions were framed.

(b) Tryout and Item Selection

The preliminary form of the institutional climate scale was tried out on 14 teacher-educators of two institutions and was also given to 15 experts for their expert advice. While administering the institutional climate scale on the teacher-educators, their critical comments were elicited. These critical comments and expert advice helped to develop the final form of the scale. In this process, some items were dropped, some modified and some new were added. The final form of the institutional climate scale has 64 items. Number of items in each dimension in preliminary and final form of the institutional climate scale is given in Table- I.

Table: I
Dimension wise Distribution of Items of Institutional Climate Scale

S. No.	Dimension	No. of Items in Initial Form	No. of Items in Final Form
I	Resources : Physical and human	13	8
II	Academic activities	15	6
III	Co-curricular activities	11	6
IV	Corporate life	12	5
V	Satisfaction with institution	11	6
VI	Alienation from institution	9	5
VII	Interpersonal relationships	10	4
VIII	Self-esteem and sense of identity	18	7
IX	Relevance of institution	11	4
X	Sense of achievement	12	6
XI	Discipline	13	7

(c) Reliability and Validity of Institutional Climate Scale

The reliability of the scale was computed using split-half method. The final form of the scale was administered on 60 teacher-educators. Coefficient of correlation between scores of odd and even items was calculated using Pearson's Product Moment formula to have reliability of half scale. The reliability of full scale was calculated by Spearman Brown Prophecy formula. The reliability of the scale, by split-half method is 0.971.

As no suitable tool measuring institutional climate of teacher education institutions was available for establishing validity by correlating scores of the two scales; content validity of the scale was established by seeking experts' opinion.

(d) Scoring

Rating on each item of institutional climate is to be done on five points: very good, good, average, poor and very poor. These items are scored by assigning

score of 5 to very good, 4 to good, 3 to average, 2 to poor and 1 to very poor. The mean of scores obtained by respondents can give a measure of the institutional climate of the institution. Raw score may be used as such for assessing institutional climate as norms for the scale has not been developed.

Conclusion

The institutional climate of the educational institution has profound impact on the all round development of the students and also on the satisfaction the teacher and non-teaching staff with their institution. The assessment of institutional climate may help to find out the factors responsible for poor perception of institutional climate by the teachers and students. These findings may help to design the programmes and take initiatives to augment the institutional climate. This institutional climate scale is reliable and easy to use. This scale is suitable for assessing institutional climate of teacher education institutions in general and those meant for training of teachers for secondary and higher secondary schools in particular.

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